

Reaction of Unsaturated Centre in Arylidene-2-aminothiazoles Towards Diazomethane

KH. m. HASSAN, M. A. EL-MAGHRABY, H. S. EL-KASHEF and A. K. EL-SHAFEI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

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Treatment of nitro-substituted arylidene-2-aminothiazoles (IV) with diazomethane gave triazolines (V). However substituents other than the nitro group in the arylidene moiety seems to inhibit this cycloaddition reaction.

ONE of the most significant contributions of the concept of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions is that of Kadaba *et al.*¹⁻⁴. Although Meerwein⁵ had earlier attempted to add diazomethane to Schiff bases, the credit for the first successful 1,3-cycloaddition to imines goes to Mustafa⁶. The reaction of nitro-substituted anils with diazomethane gave cyclic adducts to which structures such as (Ia) and (Ib) were assigned.

Mustafa postulated the initial formation of 1,2,4-triazolines (Ia) which tautomerized to the 2-isomer (Ib). His assignment was based on the fact that the adduct reverted to the anils and presumably diazomethane either by heating or hydrolysis. Buckley⁷ re-examined the reaction of diazomethane with *p*-nitro-*N*-(*p*-nitrobenzylidene) aniline and assigned the 1,2,3-triazoline structure to the product (II);

he confirmed this assignment by showing that the adduct (II) is identical with the product formed from the reaction of *p*-nitrophenyl azide with *p*-nitrostyrene.

A more extensive study of the addition of diazomethane to anils has been reported by Kadaba². His data confirm the general view that electron withdrawing group on the amine ring is apparently more effective than a similar group in the benzoylidene portion.

Experimental

All melting points were uncorrected and were obtained on a Kofler electrically heated melting point apparatus. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam IR spectrophotometer, model SP 200 G, using KBr discs. Silica gel 'chromatographic grade' was used for preparing chromatoplates.

2-Aminothiazoles (III)

These compounds were prepared by the reaction between ketones, thiourea and iodine according to the method given by Dodson and King⁸.

Arylidene-2-aminothiazoles (IV)

A mixture of equimolecular amounts of 2-aminothiazole derivative and aldehyde in 50 ml ethanol and 0.2 ml piperidine was refluxed for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and the product which separated on cooling was filtered off at the pump. The product was crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 1.

1,2,3-Triazolines (V)

Ethereal solutions of 1 g each of the Schiff bases was treated with excess of cold ethereal diazomethane. The reaction mixture was kept at -5° for 15 days, during which fresh amounts of ethereal diazomethane solution were added. The ether was then evaporated and in every case the products were filtered off, washed with light petroleum ether (40-60) and crystallized from the proper solvent. For Schiff bases having substituents other than the nitro group in the arylidene moiety, the crude products showed the properties of the starting compounds, even after the action of diazomethane for a long time (*ca* 30 days). The results are listed in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation, a new series of Schiff bases were prepared by the interaction of 2-aminothiazoles III, with substituted aromatic aldehydes.

TABLE 1.—ARYLIDENE-2-AMINOTHAZOLES

Comp. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.P. °C	Yield %	ν(ir) (cm ⁻¹)	Analytical data					
							Calculated (%)			Found (%)		
							C	H	N	C	H	N
IV a	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	105-6	70	C=N 1615 NO ₂ 1540	62.14	3.56	13.59	62.28	3.71	13.73
b	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	113-4	73	C=N 1615 NO ₂ 1550	62.14	3.56	13.59	62.32	3.899	13.70
c	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	154-5	76	C=N 1618 NO ₂ 1545	62.14	3.56	13.59	62.05	3.80	13.45
d	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄ -	109-10	80	C=N 1620 OH 3350	68.57	4.29	10.00	68.45	4.15	10.16
e	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅ -	191-2	85	C=N 1630 C=C 1610	74.48	4.83	9.66	74.38	4.70	9.55
f	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	139-40	90	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1550	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.05	4.18	12.85
g	<i>p</i> CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	158-9	65	C=N 1618 NO ₂ 1540	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.26	4.11	13.06
h	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	193-4	68	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1540	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.32	4.09	13.25
i	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	92-3	70	C=N 1615 NO ₂ 1550	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.12	3.85	13.11
j	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	103-4	76	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1540	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.32	4.15	13.33
k	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	135-6	82	C=N 1618 NO ₂ 1550	63.16	4.02	13.00	63.29	4.35	13.45
l	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	141-2	78	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1550	64.09	4.45	12.46	64.15	4.73	12.09
m	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	122-3	69	C=N 1622 NO ₂ 1540	64.09	4.45	12.46	64.15	4.55	12.33
n	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	168-9	80	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1550	64.09	4.45	12.46	64.33	4.17	12.12
o	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₅ -	155-6	79	C=N 1625 C=C 1610	75.47	5.06	8.81	75.18	5.34	8.66
p	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	196-7	40	C=N 1620 NO ₂ 1550	43.17	2.16	20.14	43.15	2.08	19.85
q	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	300	38	C=N 1615 NO ₂ 1545	50.19	3.42	15.97	50.46	3.25	15.73

TABLE 2.—1' 2, 3-TRIAZOLINES

Comp. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.P. °C	Yield %	ν(ir) (cm ⁻¹)	Analytical data					
							Calculated (%)			Found (%)		
							C	H	N	C	H	N
V a	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	96-7	35	N=N 1580 C-N 1055	58.12	3.70	19.94	57.85	3.45	19.86
b	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	115-6	30	N=N 1570 C-N 1060	58.12	3.70	19.94	57.98	3.85	19.78
c	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	138-9	33	N=N 1575 C-N 1060	58.12	3.70	19.94	58.09	3.66	19.67
d	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	145-6	30	N=N 1580 C-N 1055	59.18	4.11	19.18	58.88	4.22	19.29
e	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	131-2	33	N=N 1570 C-N 1045	59.18	4.11	19.18	59.26	4.06	19.32
f	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	160-1	35	N=N 1575 C-N 1055	59.18	4.11	19.18	59.32	4.35	19.02
g	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	141-2	30	N=N 1580 C-N 1060	59.18	4.11	19.18	58.96	4.09	19.15
h	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	138-9	32	N=N 1585 C-N 1055	59.18	4.11	19.18	59.26	3.89	19.45
i	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	105-6	38	N=N 1575 C-N 1050	59.18	4.11	19.18	59.22	3.92	19.24
j	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	86-7	35	N=N 1575 C-N 1045	60.16	4.49	18.47	60.36	4.45	18.33
k	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	119-20	35	N=N 1580 C-N 1060	60.16	4.49	18.47	59.88	4.18	18.25
l	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	124-5	30	N=N 1585 C-N 1060	60.16	4.49	18.47	60.19	4.26	18.44
m	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	180-1	20	N=N 1575	41.25	2.50	26.25	41.10	2.35	26.11

The reaction proceeded smoothly in ethanol and in the presence of piperidine as a catalyst giving a quantitative yield of IV.

The time of reaction and purity of compounds were controlled by thin layer chromatoplates. The structures of IV were based on the correct elemental analyses and IR spectra of these compounds showing a characteristic absorption band corresponding to $\nu_{C=N}$ in the 1630–1615 cm^{-1} region, and a strong band in the 1550–1540 cm^{-1} range which is due to the stretching vibration of the NO_2 entity (cf. Table 1).

The action of diazomethane on these Schiff bases was studied. The reaction proceeded in dry ethereal solution at -5° , for 15 days. However, compounds (IV, d,e,o,q) were regenerated unreacted from the reaction mixture after a long time *ca* 30 days.

The greater sensitivity of the reaction due to the presence of an electron withdrawing group either in the arylidene moiety or in the anil portion of the compound indicates that the formation of the C–C bond in the transition state is relatively much in advance of that of the N–N bond. The effect of the electron withdrawing group would then be to stabilize

the developing negative charge on the nitrogen atom. From the previous results, the following mechanism may be suggested which seems consistent with the data given by Buckley⁷ (Scheme 1). The analytical data as well as the IR spectra of the cycloadducts support the 1,2,3-triazoline structure (cf. Table 2).

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